

A Simple Recreational Experiment of the 1970's Monkey Theory in an Inefficient Market

Abstract

It all started in 1973 with the best selling book, *A Random Walk Down Wall Street*, which was published by Prof. Burton G. Malkiel from Princeton University who claimed that “*A blindfolded monkey throwing darts at a newspaper's financial pages could select a portfolio that would do just as well as one carefully selected by experts*”. The experiment involved monkeys throwing darts at the stock pages each year. The process was repeated from 1964 to 2010 and they tracked the results. Surprisingly, on average, 98 of the 100 monkey portfolios beat the 1,000 stock capitalization weighted stock universe each year (*e.g. Russell 1,000 Index / Standard and Poor's 1,000 Index*). The paper aims to recreate the experiment on an inefficient market by use of similar methods (and not actual monkeys). The research experiment would be conducted by formulating many baskets of randomized stocks around late 2007 as they would be studied & tracked to see how well they hold up. The objective of this experiment is to check if the results would prove to be similar when working in an inefficient market by seeing if a randomly generated portfolio would either underperform or over perform the index.

Keywords

Efficient Market Hypothesis, BSE, S&P BSE 200

Introduction

Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH)

Burton G. Malkiel, (1989) “*A capital market is said to be efficient if it fully and correctly reflects all relevant information in determining security prices. Formally, the market is said to be efficient with respect to some information set, ϕ , if security prices would be unaffected by revealing that information to all participants. Moreover, efficiency with respect to an information set, ϕ , implies that it is impossible to make economic profits by trading on the basis of ϕ .*”

In recent years, there has been a lot of criticism with regard to both theoretical and empirical grounds of EMH. The reason as to why it is criticized is that there are a number of investors and portfolio managers “*who have beaten the market*”. The best example of a value investor is **Mr. Michael Lee-Chin**, whose investment strategy mantra is “*buy, hold, and prosper*” that he would use to make his clients wealthy and himself, too. The rebate to this argument is that if there are a

large number of participants at any given time in the market, some will outperform and most will underperform the market. EMH proponents also argue that the people who outperform the market are considered to have done it *out-of-luck* rather than *out-of-skill* due to the laws of probability.

The Indian Stock Market is considered as an *“inefficient market”*. Under the *Review of Literature* section, the necessary articles are provided to support the argument that the Indian Stock Market is not efficient in the semi-strong form.

Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE)

Currently, there are two major stock exchanges in India, *BSE Stock Exchange and NSE Stock Exchange*. The reason as to why the experiment is based on BSE is that the Bhavcopy provided by BSE with regard to the historical data is observed as more accurate than that of the NSE Bhavcopy (which was trialed and tested - on an individual basis).

Note: Bhavcopy refers to a snapshot of all the shares listed in the stock exchange on a particular day. It includes details such as:

SC_CODE Unique code assigned to a scrip of a company by BSE.

SC_NAME Name of the company.

SC_GROUP Scrip part of which group.

SC_TYPE Scrip category - Equity, Preference, Debenture or Bond.

OPEN The price at which the security first trades on a given trading day.

CLOSE The final price at which a security is traded on a given trading day.

It also entails many other details ...

Standard & Poor BSE 200 (S&P BSE 200)

S&P Dow Jones Indices, *“The S&P BSE 200 index is designed to measure the performance of the top 200 companies listed at BSE Ltd., based on size and liquidity across sectors.”*

An Overview of Index Funds

In recent times, a popular mode of investment for both amateur and seasoned investors have been *“Index Funds”*. An Index Fund is either in the form of a *“Mutual Fund Index Fund”* or an *“Exchange Traded Fund Index Fund”*.

“India's oldest exchange-traded fund, the Nippon India ETF Nifty BeES, has delivered a 16% average annual return since its launch two decades ago. A person who had invested ₹1 lakh in the ETF at its inception would now be worth ₹19.4 lakh, according to Mint's calculations.”
(Mint 2021)

The reason as to why this nifty index fund was also used as a measure in this experiment rather than a sensex index fund is because most mutual fund-index funds were established around 2013. Thus, we took into account the oldest exchange traded fund which gave us historical data up till 2001.

The Objectives of this Experiment

To analyze whether the results received are similar to that of previous research (i.e. where monkeys were able to beat the market). - an *exception* being that the study is being conducted in an *inefficient market*.

To calculate the *CAGR (Computed Annual Growth Return)* of each portfolio and benchmark it against *S&P BSE 200 & Nippon India ETF Nifty BeES*. This to see how many and which portfolios were able to beat the market indices and by what margin.

Review of Literature

Burton G. Malkiel (1989), When calculating securities prices, a capital market is said to be efficient if it accurately and precisely reflects all relevant information. Formally, if providing that information to all participants has no effect on security prices, the market is considered to be efficient with respect to a certain set of information. Furthermore, efficiency with regard to a knowledge set, ϕ , means that share prices reflect all information and consistent alpha generation is impossible. (i.e., an investor could not generate consistent excessive return)

T Mallikarjunappa & JJ Dsouza (2013), As per results of the AARs and CAARs, investors can generate abnormal returns by assessing the quarterly earnings for June 2008 and sell the stocks when the results are announced. The information adjustment process will continue until 30 days after the results are announced. Furthermore, the CAARs demonstrate that the values have been steadily declining since the June 2008 quarterly results. This shows that the market has received unfavorable signals as a result of these results. Thus, investors endure abnormal losses when buying stocks and gain abnormal profits when shorting them. An observation is that the Indian market is reluctant to react to publicly available information. This is an indicator of market

inefficiency. As a result, the research concluded that the Indian Stock Exchange is inefficient in its semi-strong form.

Bishwajeet Bhattacharjee, Sumita Dave & Shikha Sondhi (2016), *The key observation analyzing 14 years of monthly average BSE Sensex data extending from January 2000 to May 2014, via autocorrelation test and student t test (if public news has any impact on the stock price) after applying unit root test demonstrates that stock prices are random in nature. The historical data set has no bearing on security prices in the capital market. Simultaneously, public news has no substantial impact on security prices, and as a result, the market becomes inefficient in terms of available information.*

G Pernagallo & B Torrisi (2020), *The research used a novel approach based on confidence intervals for proportions in this paper to assess the degree of inefficiency in the S&P 500 Index, concluding that the weak form of efficiency should be ruled out for several stocks. The research estimated the proportion of inefficient stocks in the index to be between 12.13 percent and 27.87 percent. This validates earlier research that shows the efficiency hypothesis is not the norm and, as a result, a financial expert may be a better investment than a blinded monkey.*

Research Methodology

Research Design

Inside the secondary data (that was acquired), certain securities under the ***SC_GROUP (such as F, T, TS, Z)*** had to be excluded. Due to it not being liquidity-oriented-securities. Under the ***SC_TYPE***, certain securities such as ***bonds, debentures and preference*** had to be excluded as well in order to conduct a smooth experiment.

After acquiring relevant information from the dataset, the experiment would move on to picking out 20 baskets of randomized stocks under which, in each basket, there would be a list of 25 securities which would receive an estimated investment amount around Rs. 25,000. To keep in mind, the securities which are being randomly selected are off on the date: 01-10-2007. The randomized selection takes place by use of complex formulas.

After the randomized selection of securities and listing its share price on 01-10-2007, the experiment moves on to listing the share price of those same securities on 01-04-2022. During this period, a lot of securities' information isn't available. So, the list of delisted companies and suspended companies is used. By the help of this list and BSE's Official Website, we can gauge

as to what the current share price is worth. That is, if the company had been liquidated or suspended by BSE. If the company had amalgamated or liquidated by delisting, it would mean that the last share price is payable back to the shareholder. If the company had been suspended, it would mean that the share price is worthless. Under the **REMARKS & REMARKS_2** headers of each portfolio, the reason as to why the share-price information isn't available is provided respectively.

After taking into account liquidated companies and suspended companies, the final price of currently listed shares are drawn upon and the total return of each portfolio is ascertained. The final amount is then drawn as matured investments. Under the "**Summary**" Sheet of the Spreadsheet, The CAGR of each portfolio is drawn and benchmarked against the S&P BSE 200 & Nippon India ETF Nifty BeES to view whether the portfolios outperform or underperform.

Source of Data

The *Bhavcopy of 01-10-2007 & 01-04-2022* was acquired from the official website of BSE India. The *delisted companies list & suspended companies list* were also acquired from the official website of BSE India.

Period of Study

Study is conducted for the period of *(14 years & 6 months or 5296 days) 1/08/2007 to 01/04/2022*.

Tools Used For Analysis

Statistical tools are used to present and analyze the past and present sets of data and information.

Research Findings

In order for simpler understanding, the experiment could be visualized as follows:

Graph 1.1: A Summary of the Research Experiment with regard to its Current Value and Initial Investment

PARTICULARS

Source: Bombay Stock Exchange - Bhavcopy

By the above chart, we could come to an observation that most of the randomized portfolios do not outperform the indices (such as S&P BSE 200 & Nippon India ETF Nifty BeES). The **CAGR returns** of Indices provided an average **9.16% p.a.** and **9.96% p.a.**. Among the 20 portfolios, 4 outperformed the market indices. The portfolios that outperformed are: **Portfolio 4, Portfolio 6, Portfolio 7 and Portfolio 18**. The table below shows the list of portfolios along with their **INITIAL_INVESTMENT, CURRENT_VALUE, NO._OF_YEARS, PROFIT/LOSS, NO._OF_STOCKS, CAGR_RETURNS (Per Annum)**.

PARTICULARS	INITIAL_INVESTMENT	CURRENT_VALUE	NO._OF_YEARS	PROFIT/LOSS	NO._OF_STOCKS	CAGR_RETURNS_(Per_Annum)
S&P BSE 200	24,651	84,128	14 Years & 6 Months	59,477	1	9.16
Nippon India ETF Nifty BeES	25,096.50	93,555	14 Years & 6 Months	68,459	1	9.96
Portfolio 1	26,108.81	27,626.47	14 Years & 6 Months	1,518	18	0.4
Portfolio 2	23,993.09	47,001.60	14 Years & 6 Months	23,009	21	4.92
Portfolio 3	27,563.13	73,966.50	14 Years & 6 Months	46,403	17	7.31
Portfolio 4	22,942.53	138,764.54	14 Years & 6 Months	115,822	20	13.72
Portfolio 5	25,779.55	54,902.55	14 Years & 6 Months	29,123	23	5.55
Portfolio 6	24,144.43	92,140.46	14 Years & 6 Months	67,996	19	10.04
Portfolio 7	23,464.19	95,425.46	14 Years & 6 Months	71,961	16	10.54
Portfolio 8	25,121.32	66,312.15	14 Years & 6 Months	41,191	19	7.18
Portfolio 9	23,971.60	47,496.44	14 Years & 6 Months	23,525	14	5.01
Portfolio 10	25,585.10	71,024.17	14 Years & 6 Months	45,439	17	7.57
Portfolio 11	24,159.98	30,620.56	14 Years & 6 Months	6,461	18	1.71
Portfolio 12	24,026.37	36,081.24	14 Years & 6 Months	12,055	17	2.95
Portfolio 13	23,422.10	36,991.19	14 Years & 6 Months	13,569	22	3.32
Portfolio 14	24,217.21	38,829.26	14 Years & 6 Months	14,612	15	3.43
Portfolio 15	22,785.35	61,586.40	14 Years & 6 Months	38,801	18	7.36
Portfolio 16	29,500.92	87,270.40	14 Years & 6 Months	57,769	22	8.06
Portfolio 17	23,266.25	69,422.62	14 Years & 6 Months	46,156	16	8.12
Portfolio 18	25,591.10	108,196.46	14 Years & 6 Months	82,605	17	10.85
Portfolio 19	24,516.00	61,323.97	14 Years & 6 Months	36,808	19	6.77
Portfolio 20	27,648.35	29,851.31	14 Years & 6 Months	2,203	16	0.55

Things To Keep In Mind:

- During the period of study, the Stock Market had experienced 2 Major Crashes: **2008 Financial Crisis and 2020 COVID-19 Pandemic**.
- While selecting the starting period of the study (**01-10-2007**), the market was in a state of bull-run and the randomized stocks were picked up right before the **2008 Financial Crisis** (this caused a lot of those selected-randomized-stocks to be **delisted** in a couple of years).
- The **earliest period of the Bhavcopy** available in the official website of BSE was **01-10-2007**.

Conclusion

As stated earlier, among the 20 randomized portfolios, only 4 portfolios managed to outperform the market in terms of indices (such as S&P BSE 200 & Nippon India ETF Nifty BeES). Thus, we could conclude that the experiment did not achieve similar results to that of the statement provided by **Burton G. Malkiel (1989)**. The research aligned to that of **G Pernagallo & B Torrisi (2020)**. The only exception being to the current research is that **the original 1970s monkey theory** had been conducted under a **strong efficient market** whereas the current research is undertaken in **an inefficient market**. The other conclusion that could be drawn is that a

randomized generated portfolio would not provide good returns in the long-term (especially in the Indian Stock Market). Thus, choosing random securities is highly cautioned.

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